

Physical Facilities and Library Situation as Correlates of Academic Staff Job Performance in Southwest Nigerian Universities

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between physical facilities, library resources, and academic staff job performance in public universities in Southwest Nigeria. Two hypotheses were tested: the significance of physical facilities and library situations as correlates of academic staff job performance. A descriptive survey design was employed, targeting 8,724 academic staff across 19 universities, with a sample of 1,320 academic staff selected using multi-stage sampling techniques. Data collection involved two instruments: the Physical Facilities and Library Situation Questionnaire (PFLSQ) and the Academic Staff Job Performance Questionnaire (ASJPQ), both of which demonstrated high reliability coefficients of 0.79 and 0.82, respectively. Analysis was conducted using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings revealed a significant relationship between physical facilities and academic staff job performance ($r = 0.514$, $p < 0.05$). This underscores the impact of well-maintained infrastructure on the effectiveness of teaching, research, and community service. Literature corroborates these findings, highlighting the essential role of adequate facilities in enhancing staff productivity. Conversely, no significant relationship was found between library situation and job performance ($r = 0.023$, $p > 0.05$), suggesting that library resources may not directly influence the performance of academic staff. These results emphasize the critical role of physical facilities in shaping academic outcomes, whereas libraries, while valuable, do not significantly correlate with job performance. Recommendations include prioritizing the upgrading of physical facilities to support academic staff performance while maintaining baseline library resources for comprehensive learning.

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Introduction

Well-resourced universities play key roles in thriving economies all over the world. Universities are typically thought of as locations for higher education and basic research. Universities may have been founded with the intention of producing middle-to upper-class citizens who might lead the charge in constructing the nation. Universities, according to Nagbi and Micah (2019), generate human resources whose actions result in increased productivity. Universities in Nigeria are under similar pressure to create the calibre and quantity of skilled workers that will propel the country out of its current developmental phase and into the developed world. Considering the aforementioned, the academic staff at Nigerian institutions would be held responsible for any uncertainties over their capacity to meet this standard. The calibre of a university's academic staff is a reliable indicator of that institution's overall performance on the job.

Professors and other members of the academic staff play an essential role in colleges and universities. Colleges and universities rely on their academic staff, who are experts in their fields, to carry out a variety of duties related to teaching, research, and other academic programs. Due to their position as the institutions' primary instructional implementers, academic staff members play an essential but sometimes overlooked role in the growth of educational institutions. Teaching staff from tertiary institutions make up the Academic Staff. Teaching, research, and community service are the three main responsibilities they carry out at the institutions.

The academic staff plays a crucial role in the country's human resource development by training future workers. According to Folunso, et al. (2014), academic staff job performance is crucial because universities produce the teachers needed for Universal Basic Education, the skilled medical professionals, nurses, and community workers needed for improved welfare and healthcare facilities, and the accountants, economists, and journalists needed for stronger private companies and better governance.

The teaching of students, the amount of research done by university staff, and the community activities offered by staff are all ways to measure academic staff job performance at Nigerian tertiary institutions. The duties of academic staff in universities have been listed as follows: lecturing, acting as examiner, helping in the lab, supervising student projects, conducting research, guiding junior lecturers, developing curricula, and helping with departmental administration (FRN, 2013). Therefore, these and other similar responsibilities are necessary for evaluating academic staff performance on the job. An academic staff member at a university must plan and implement instructional strategies that will promote effective learning, engage in research, assess students' performance, teach effectively, manage time for teaching, maintain discipline among staff members, guide students, treat them fairly, and motivate them to higher achievements in order to be considered productive.

Researchers have found that academic staff in universities are not meeting expectations in their job performance. Some undergraduates I spoke with felt that professors don't put enough thought into their lectures, which shows in their shaky delivery and incomplete coverage of the material. Other students felt that professors use antiquated teaching techniques and don't use any modern pedagogical innovations. Inaccessible professors and other academic staff members have been a source of irritation for some students. Delays in responding to emails or insufficient assistance with personal or academic matters are examples of what may be considered difficulties. In terms of teaching, the researcher also noted that some academic staff members don't appear to be on time for class, while others

who are on time at the institution don't bother to show up. It appears that several members of the academic staff lack a solid grasp of the provided material. Many professors already know that their students will not learn anything new until the final exam is almost here.

There have been reports of academic staff members who fail to show up for exam supervision; in some instances, this delicate responsibility is given to graduate students, and this has significantly exacerbated the problem of exam fraud plaguing numerous Nigerian universities. There have also been reports of academic staff exploiting graduating students as tutors, data entry clerks, and data entry clerks.

Tertiary education includes research and development as a component. The number and quality of articles published is said to be a good indicator of research productivity. A university's standing in the community, nation, and world is greatly enhanced by the calibre of its research and the ripple effect it has on these areas. The significance and excellence of a university's research is the most important factor in determining its standing and reputation. Lack of incentives for research and publication appears to be contributing to a decrease in the quality of research among academic staff at institutions. The conduct of research and the creation of high-quality papers for publishing are also challenges for some academic staff. Educators who don't keep themselves informed will almost definitely have little to no impact on the field's progress. The "decline effect" is a real thing in academic research, according to Lehrer (2020). It draws attention to cases where preliminary research shows promising results but later studies don't confirm them, pointing to a possible drop in the calibre of academic staff research. As Horton (2015) pointed out, there are problems with the way academic studies and peer reviews are done now.

At times, members of academic staff fail to advance in their careers as a result of stagnation in their field of expertise or an absence of scholarly publications. To take care of their personal families, many academic staff members carefully plan how to spend their limited earnings. For an extended period, it seems like some people are stuck with their entry-level academic credentials because of a lack of funding. It has come to light in recent years that a number of academic staff members, who are an integral part of the Nigerian university system, appear to lack the commitment necessary to ensure the success of the entire educational system, particularly the university sector.

Advisory board membership and journal refereeing are two examples of community service that academic staff members may engage in. Seminars or empowerment programs focused on adult literacy could be a way for them to impart their wisdom. Bringle (2019) confirmed, among other things, that certain academic staff appear to be disinterested in carrying out public enlightenment programs. Academic staff in universities cannot overstate the value of teaching, research, and community involvement. One wonders if the loss in academic staff job performance is not a reflection of the physical facilities and library situation at universities given the observed decline in academic staff job performance.

In addition to teacher and student inputs, the amount, quality, and usefulness of physical resources are equally vital for ensuring the quality of university education. The reason behind this is that without proper planning, the operations of both students and staff would be ineffective since the necessary facilities, equipment, and resources will not be available when they are needed. The physical facilities and environment of educational institutions determine the right shape and atmosphere for teaching and learning, according to Uche, et al. (2016), who emphasised the significance of this. In terms of staff and student friendliness,

outsider appeal, aesthetics, healthiness, safety, currency, and relevance, these facilities reflect the institution's quality.

Visualising physical facilities and educational goals as closely interwoven and interdependent is essential for creating an effective teaching and learning environment. The comfort, safety, and performance of academic staff and students are greatly impacted by these physical facilities, which serve as the learning environment. Because of the importance of physical facilities to the implementation process, they should be readily available. In order to create and accredit a university in Nigeria, there must be physical facilities available. All the following physical facilities should normally be available: classrooms and administrative buildings, dorms for students, restrooms, a football field, lawns, a canteen, a plant house, a security post, a gymnasium, a health centre, laboratories, and more.

Academic institutions' physical facilities may or may not be adequate, of high quality, or fully operational, regardless of their availability. Effective teaching and learning, and by extension, the job performance of academic staff, seem to be seriously impacted by the poor quality and utilisation of facilities. The physical facilities should not only be provided, but also of excellent quality and fully operational. The researcher saw that certain institutions have dormitories that are overcrowded and classrooms that are in poor condition, with most of the floors and walls in a dangerously disrepair state. In addition to some university buildings sometimes being in poor condition with cracked walls or a leaking roof, it is not uncommon for doors and windows to become inoperable, leading to a sense of vulnerability. Again, some campuses seem to have poorly managed grounds, which could be an indication that conservation facilities are either unavailable or not well cared for (Asiyai, 2017). Research and teaching are both negatively impacted by the situation's poor study atmosphere.

It would appear that some members of the academic staff work out of shared offices, while others work from wherever there is a tree or under a building that offers them an office. In order to support their online teaching program, some academic staff may not have access to reliable internet connections and steady lighting in their offices. In Southwest Nigeria, the researcher found that most departments' facilities were severely lacking for either lectures or practicals at certain universities. The research found that certain academic staff members lack offices, that classroom sizes are too small to allow for meaningful interaction between teachers and students, and that the academic environment is unhealthy due to decaying, inefficient, and dilapidated infrastructure facilities.

The purpose of every academic library is to assist the academic programs of the institution by offering pertinent material in order to meet the ever-increasing information demands of the users, which include the university's students and academic staff. It is the goal of most academic libraries to increase the use, accessibility, and availability of information through their acquisition, organisation, storage, and dissemination of materials. There is no more crucial support system for academic research than university libraries. Many different types of library materials are required in order for libraries to adequately facilitate research. Labour, funds, and a library's stock of books are all resources that must be supplied.

In order to encourage research, well-stocked libraries can be a valuable asset to educational institutions. Research can be facilitated by libraries that have e-journals, fast internet, and other facilities. Journals offer a useful way for academic staff to learn about different types of research output and can be a great way to identify areas that need more research. In addition to having out-of-date books and scant electronic connectedness in the main library, the researcher found that certain university libraries seemed to be completely devoid of any

books whatsoever. Poor job performance by academic staff appears to be influenced by this. The library should have a enough number of books to cover all aspects of the subject, with one book for every ten students.

The main purpose of the study was to examine physical facilities and library situation as correlates of academic staff job performance in Southwest Nigerian Universities. The following research hypotheses were formulated for this study

1. There is no significant relationship between physical facilities situation and academic staff job performance
2. There is no significant relationship between library situation and academic staff job performance

Literature Review

Physical Facilities Situation and Staff Job Performance

Olatunji (2013) examined the disparities in availability, appropriateness, and functionality of several physical facilities in Edo State. The results indicated that decentralisation enhances the availability, adequacy, and functionality of school physical facilities.

Ajayi and Abiodun-Oyebanji (2010) demonstrated that factors related to resource conditions, including physical resources, material resources, human resources, and social amenities, collectively and significantly influenced academic staff job performance. The study indicates that just 9.4 percent of the variation in academic staff job performance is attributable to the combined influence of resource situational factors. This indicates that factors beyond those examined in the study significantly influenced the variation in academic staff job performance. In terms of the relative contributions of resource variables, only physical and human resources were substantial, whereas material resources and social amenities were not. This implies that elements related to resource availability, such as physical and human resources, are more critical in improving academic staff job performance.

Olayanju and Asogwa (2010) assert that it is illogical to anticipate that academic staff can be effective or excel in curriculum development without adequate foundational infrastructure and facilities for teaching and learning. Oyedeji (2012) asserts a strong and significant correlation between infrastructure development and the success variables of tertiary institutions, including research publications, faculty performance, institutional discipline, and community service. Bello (2011) concluded that proper infrastructure facilities are necessary for the efficiency of lecturers' work.

Hasbullah (2011) conducted a study to ascertain the importance of physical resources in the teaching and learning process about the quality of higher educational standards. He conducted an analysis and concluded that physical resources significantly influence teacher performance. Hadagali et al. (2012) conducted a study examining the productivity of academic staff at public universities in relation to the work environment backdrop. The findings indicate that the working environment significantly influenced the teaching and research endeavours of the professors. Osagie, and Okafor, (2012) found that university lecturers cannot perform effectively in curriculum development without sufficient fundamental facilities for teaching, learning, and research.

It can be inferred that physical facilities may be related to job performance. This study aims to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the condition of physical facilities and the job performance of academic staff in institutions located in Southwest Nigeria, based on the examined literature.

Library Situation and Academic Staff Job Performance

Nagbi and Micah (2019) assert that library development significantly influences the job performance of academic staff. The study concluded that there is a positive correlation between TETFund and the enhancement of library collections in universities. Conversely, they asserted that its activities lack a significant correlation with the development of Federal Universities in Nigeria within the study's designated timeframe.

It is so concluded that the provision of a well-equipped library will enhance academic staff commitment and patriotism in fulfilling their responsibilities, thereby improving their performance. This study aims to investigate the important association between library conditions and the job performance of academic staff in universities located in Southwest Nigeria, based on a review of relevant literature.

Materials and Methods

The study adopted a descriptive research design of the survey type, deemed appropriate for collecting information from a representative sample in their natural settings. This approach facilitated an exploration of the resource situation and academic staff job performance in public universities in Southwest Nigeria. The population consisted of 8,724 academic staff across 19 public universities, comprising 12 state-owned and 7 federal institutions spread across six states: Lagos, Ogun, Oyo, Osun, Ondo, and Ekiti. The sample included 1,320 academic staff from six public universities, selected through a multi-stage sampling technique. The process involved choosing three states via simple random sampling, followed by the selection of one federal and one state university from each state through stratified random sampling. Academic departments and individual staff members were subsequently chosen using proportionate sampling.

Two instruments were employed to collect data: The Physical Facilities and Library Situation Questionnaire (PFLSQ) and the Academic Staff Job Performance Questionnaire (ASJPQ). The PFLSQ gathered data on resource availability, including physical facilities, instructional materials, ICT resources, funding, human resources, and libraries, using a 4-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree. The ASJPQ assessed academic staff performance in teaching, research/publication, and community service, utilising a 5-point Likert scale from Excellent to Poor. Section A of each instrument focused on demographic information, while other sections contained specific items to evaluate the respective domains. Validity was ensured through expert review by the researcher's supervisor and specialists in Tests and Measurement and Educational Management, who refined the instruments for clarity and appropriateness.

Reliability of the instruments was established using the test-retest method. The questionnaires were administered twice to 40 academic staff and four heads of departments in two universities excluded from the main sample, with a two-week interval between tests. The reliability coefficients, calculated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation, were 0.79 for the PFLSQ and 0.82 for the ASJPQ, indicating high reliability. The instruments were administered directly by the researcher and six assistants, with permission from university authorities. A direct delivery and recovery method ensured a high response rate. Data collection followed a structured process, targeting both academic staff and their heads of departments for comprehensive insights.

Data analysis involved descriptive statistics for summarising responses and inferential statistics for hypothesis testing. Frequency counts, percentages, means, and standard

deviations addressed the research questions, while Pearson's Product Moment Correlation was used to test hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between physical facilities situation and academic staff job performance

Table 1: Relationship between resource physical facilities situation and academic staff job performance

Variables	N	Mean	Stand Dev	r-cal	P-value
Physical Facilities Situation	1153	17.40	3.49	0.514*	0.000
Job Performance	1153	85.05	5.56		

*P<0.05

Table 1 showed that the r-cal value of 0.514 is significant at 0.05 level of significance because the P-value (0.000) < 0.05. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between physical facilities situation and academic staff job performance in Southwest Nigerian Universities.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between library situation and academic staff job performance

Table 2: Relationship between library situation and academic staff job performance

Variables	N	Mean	Stand Dev	r-cal	P-value
Library Situation	1153	12.90	3.39	0.023	0.439
Job Performance	1153	85.05	5.56		

P>0.05

Table 2 showed that the r-cal value of 0.023 is not significant at 0.05 level of significance because the P-value (0.439) > 0.05. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is no significant relationship between library situation and academic staff job performance in Southwest Nigerian Universities.

Discussion

The study revealed that there was a significant relationship between physical facilities situation and academic staff job performance. The significant relationship between physical facilities and academic staff job performance suggests that the quality and adequacy of the physical infrastructure within an educational institution directly impact the effectiveness and efficiency of academic staff. In line with this finding, Bello (2011) came to the conclusion that the provision of adequate infrastructure facilities is essential to the efficiency of the job performed by lecturers. Hasbullah (2011) found that physical resources have a substantial impact on the performance of teachers. According to Regina (2014), university lecturers are unable to function at a high level in the field of curriculum if they are not provided with adequate basic facilities for teaching, learning, and research.

It was revealed that there was no significant relationship between library situation and academic staff job performance. The absence of a significant relationship between library situation and academic staff job performance suggests that the physical or operational state of the library, as perceived by academic staff, may not be a critical factor influencing their job performance. In contrast to this finding, Nagbi and Micah (2019) concluded that library plays a vital part in academic staff job performance.

Conclusion

It was concluded that as physical facilities were determinants of academic staff job performance in universities as library situation has no influence on academic staff job performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made

1. The university management should invest in upgrading physical facilities to align with modern educational requirements for better job performance of the academic staff.
2. While the library situation is not a significant contributor to job performance, the university management should maintain a baseline level of library resources which could enhance comprehensive learning.

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